

Linnæus University

Monthly Report January 2025

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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CONTENTS

Summary report.....	3
1. Overview.....	3
2. Results.....	3
2.1 Data collection	3
2.2 Genomics summary	9
3. Conclusion.....	10

SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. Data included in this report are based on samples collected from September 2024 to January 2025 and that previously have not been published.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report (published on 9th of January; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620065>), and as of 17th January 2025, test results have been submitted for 2126 samples taken from 1135 individual wild birds representing 21 species across five nodes in Europe (Table 1). Of the 2126 collected samples, 970 were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 578 cloacal swabs, 367 faecal samples, 138 feather samples, 37 combined swabs (choana + cloacal), and 36 environmental samples. Of all samples, 280 (13.2 %) from five different species were positive for avian influenza virus, of which none were positive for HPAI virus (Figure 1; Table 2).

The overall bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in these recently submitted samples was 20.5 %. The highest bird-level prevalence was found in Sweden (28.6 %; Table 1), and among the most frequently sampled birds, Mallard had a prevalence of 28.6 % (203 of 710 individuals), Barnacle Goose of 12.8 % (7 of 55 individuals), and Eurasian Teal of 9.8 % (20 of 204 individuals) (Table 1).

TABLE 1 Total number of individuals sampled in the wild (mussels and birds; including recaptures of some birds), as well as number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza in the respective country. The table includes samples from September 2024 to January 2025, previously never published.

Group/species	Node 2 Sweden		Node 2 Lithuania		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total	
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																
Mute Swan							1	0							1	0
Barnacle Goose	55	7													55	7
Ruddy Shelduck							2	0							2	0
Mallard	641	198					24	0	15	0	3	1	27	4	710	203
Eurasian Wigeon	1	0													1	0
Marbled Duck												1	0	1	0	
Eurasian Teal	75	19					2	0	123	1	4	0		204	20	
Pochard							1	0						1	0	
Red-crested Pochard												3	0	3	0	
Ferruginous Duck												2	0	2	0	
Tufted Duck							3	0						3	0	
Velvet Scoter			1	0										1	0	
<i>Grebes</i>																
Great Crested Grebe					1	0									1	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																
Great Cormorant	7	0													7	0
<i>Rails</i>																
Common Moorhen												6	0	6	0	
Eurasian Coot							4	0				69	0	73	0	
Red-knobbed Coot												12	0	12	0	
<i>Waders</i>																
Common Ringed Plover	1	0													1	0
Grey Plover	2	1													2	1
European Golden Plover	2	0													2	0
Purple Sandpiper	3	0													3	0
Dunlin	1	0													1	0
Common Snipe	1	0													1	0
Jack Snipe	4	0													4	0
<i>Larids</i>																
Black-headed Gull							1	0							1	0
European Herring Gull	2	2													2	2
Yellow-legged Gull							2	0							2	0
<i>Others</i>																
Unknown Species							2	0				1	0		3	0
Mussel							30	0							30	0
Total	795	227	1	0	1	0	72	0	138	1	7	1	121	4	1135	233

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FIGURE 1 Sample sites for the 1135 wild birds and mussels sampled in five European countries, yielding 280 samples positive for avian influenza virus. The figure only includes samples from September 2024 to January 2025, previously never published.

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TABLE 2 Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus, in the respective country. Table only includes samples for the current reporting period (September 2024 to January 2025), previously never published.

Group/species	Node 2 Sweden			Node 2 Lithuania			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI
<i>Waterfowl</i>																								
Mute Swan										1	0	0										1	0	0
Barnacle Goose	55	7	0																			55	7	0
Ruddy Shelduck										2	0	0										2	0	0
Mallard	1178	236	0							24	0	0	45	0	0	6	1	0	45	9	0	1298	246	0
Eurasian Wigeon	2	0	0																			2	0	0
Marbled Duck																			2	0	0	2	0	0
Eurasian Teal	125	23	0							2	0	0	369	1	0	8	0	0				504	24	0
Pochard										1	0	0										1	0	0
Red-crested Pochard																			6	0	0	6	0	0
Ferruginous Duck																			4	0	0	4	0	0
Tufted Duck										3	0	0										3	0	0
Velvet Scoter				1	0	0																1	0	0
<i>Grebes</i>																								
Great Crested Grebe							2	0	0													2	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																								
Great Cormorant	14	0	0																			14	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																								
Common Moorhen																			12	0	0	12	0	0
Eurasian Coot										4	0	0							137	0	0	141	0	0
Red-knobbed Coot																			24	0	0	24	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																								
Common Ringed Plover	1	0	0																			1	0	0
Grey Plover	2	1	0																			2	1	0
European Golden Plover	2	0	0																			2	0	0
Purple Sandpiper	3	0	0																			3	0	0
Dunlin	1	0	0																			1	0	0
Common Snipe	1	0	0																			1	0	0
Jack Snipe	4	0	0																			4	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																								
Black-headed Gull										1	0	0										1	0	0
European Herring Gull	4	2	0																			4	2	0
Yellow-legged Gull										2	0	0										2	0	0
<i>Others</i>																								
Unknown Species										2	0	0							1	0	0	3	0	0
Muscel										30	0	0										30	0	0
Total	1392	269	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	72	0	0	414	1	0	14	1	0	231	9	0	2126	280	0

A weekly compilation of all 3743 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), sampled at each node from August 2024 to January 2025, can be seen in Figure 2.

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FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of samples collected at each node, and all nodes combined, from week 34, 2024 to week 3, 2025. In total, 3743 samples (negative samples in blue; avian influenza virus-positive samples in orange) have been collected at six nodes between August 2024 and January 2025, yielding 416 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 22 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 9th of January (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620065>), and as of 17th January 2025, a total of six new sequences have been generated from samples positive for H5 avian influenza viruses. All six samples were collected from Mallards in Sweden (Node 2) and five were confirmed to be H5N3, whilst the final sample was H5Nx, where the N-type could not be determined. Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences found that they belonged to the Eurasian Avian non-Goose Guangdong (EA-nonGsGd) low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) clade. The HA sequences of these samples were similar to the H5N2 LPAI virus previously detected at Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (see November 2024 report: <https://zenodo.org/records/14507721>) (Figure 3). The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea

FIGURE 3 Phylogenetic analyses of the HA sequences generated by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea. Image of a subset of the HA tree displaying the sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea.

In addition, a further 29 genome sequences were generated from samples positive for non-H5 avian influenza viruses. All these samples were collected from Mallards in Sweden (Node 2) and displayed wide subtypic diversity (3 x H1N2, 4 x H2N3, 2 x H2N6, 2 x H2N9, 1 x H3N8, 1 x H4N2, 4 x H4N6, 1 x H4N9, 1 x H8N7, 1 x H9N2, 1 x H10N4, 1 x H11N3, 1 x H11N6 and 6 x H11N9). Interestingly, a number of these sequences were generated from samples where multiple subtypes were detected (particularly faecal and cloacal swab samples), which could be suggestive of mixed infections with multiple avian influenza virus subtypes.

3. CONCLUSION

Substantially more samples have now been analysed and included in this report, with the majority originating from Sweden. The backlog of analysed samples spans the period from September 2024 to January 2025. The peak in the number of samples, as well as the peak in prevalence, was observed in week 44, with a prevalence rate of 28.6 %. These results are primarily based on samples collected from Mallards in Sweden. Positive samples for avian influenza virus in Mallards are common in Sweden (particularly at Ottenby, where the wild bird trap is located) during the autumn migration. While the proportion of positive samples is relatively high, the small number of HPAI cases indicates that there is no immediate concern for the overall avian influenza situation.